

THE GERMAN GEODETIC COMMISSION (DGK) AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO GGOS

GGOS DAYS, NOV. 14TH, 2022 MUNICH, GERMANY

Harald Schuh (Chair DGK)

Urs Hugentobler (Secretary General DGK)

Helmut Hornik (Acting Director, DGK Office)

TASKS OF DGK

THE DGK REPRESENTS GEODETIC RESEARCH AND
UNIVERSITY TEACHING IN GERMANY

TASKS INCLUDE:

- Scientific research on all topics of geodesy (in a broad sense)
- Coordination of geodetic research in Germany
- Scientific advice and support for university and non-university institutions
- Representation of geodesy in the national and international framework
- Coordination of academic teaching and geodetic training at universities

The DGK was founded in Munich in 1952 as the German Geodetic Commission within the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities

DGK MEMBERSHIP AND DEFINITION OF GEODESY

The DGK has up to **45 full members** (professors at German universities). **Corresponding members** ensure a close link with the international scientific geodetic community. **Permanent guests** provide the connection to administration, professional and specialist associations and research institutions.

Geodesy includes (as defined by German associations)

- measuring the Earth and recording its dynamic changes globally, regionally, locally,
- Analysis, evaluation and visualization of the data obtained and processes recorded together with other spatial information,
- Development of strategies and concepts for sustainable spatial developments, urban planning, cadaster, real estate management

DIVISIONS OF DGK (I)

- Four scientific divisions "Earth Measurement", "Geoinformatics", "Engineering Geodesy" and "Land and Real Estate Management“, and the “Education and Teaching" division
- As an action-oriented component of spatial development and land policy, **Land and Real Estate Management** includes all planning and development processes as well as evaluation and regulatory measures for the use of land and urban structures.
- **Engineering Geodesy** is the discipline of recording, setting out and monitoring local and regional geometry-related phenomena with special consideration of quality, sensors and reference systems.

DIVISIONS OF DGK (II)

- **Geoinformatics** deals with the development and application of informational methods for modeling and acquisition, exchange, exploration, analysis, synthesis and evaluation of data on space-time variant geo-phenomena.
- The **Education and Teaching** division creates the connection between the four scientific divisions and the university education. It deals with the skills and qualifications of geodesy students with regard to research and the professional world in an international context.

DIVISIONS OF DGK (III)

Earth Measurement (Higher Geodesy, Satellite Geodesy)

Different phenomena such as the shape of the Earth, fluctuations in the Earth's rotation or the gravitational field are studied.

- For this purpose, various geodetic methods are developed and used to record, model and interpret components of the Earth system on various spatial and temporal scales.
- Geometric and gravimetric data are collected with high accuracy using complementary sensor systems and satellite missions, and are checked and validated using independent methods. Stored and archived in data bases within national and international cooperation.

FURTHER CONTENTS

- Selected activities of DGK Divisions
- Student numbers
- Social Media Campaign to attract students
- Other activities and outreach

SELECTED ACTIVITIES OF DGK-DIVISIONS

Research efforts of the divisions are detailed in the DGK Yearbook 2022, bi-annual, in reduced format

Division Geoinformatics

- PhD Students colloquia

Division Engineering Geodesy

- Workshops
- PhD Students colloquia

Division Land and Real Estate Management

- PhD Students colloquia

SELECTED ACTIVITIES OF DGK-DIVISIONS

Division “Earth Measurement” (Higher Geodesy, Satellite Geodesy)

- Information exchange and coordination with relevant federal offices and organizations (BKG, BFG, BSH, AdV, ...) in the field of geodesy
- Exchange about and coordination of ongoing and planned research (joint research projects, research units of DFG, SFBs, ...)
- Involvement in international organizations, e.g., IUGG and IAG
- Contribution to GGOS, for instance establishment of GGOS-DACH (German speaking countries) in 2021
- **Preparation of IUGG General Assembly in Berlin, 12-19 July 2023**

Welcome to the

**28th IUGG
General Assembly
July 2023**

Berlin

Photo: shutter

City Cube Berlin – Venue for the 28th IUGG General Assembly

12th to 19th of July 2023

<https://www.iugg2023berlin.org>

Organizers:

GFZ

Helmholtz Centre
POTSDAM

BGR

GGOS Days 2022

**Save
the Date**
**11–20 July
2023**

Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31						

Scientific Programme of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics

OUR SUPPORTERS AT PRESENT

GFZ

Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR)

AWI

Geomar

Geo.X

Bundesamt für Kartografie und Geodäsie (BKG)

Others?

WEBSITE:

<https://www.IUGG2023BERLIN.ORG>

MATERIAL FOR DISTRIBUTION

[SHARE POINT](#)

- Roll ups
- Post cards
- Flyers
- Questionnaire for booking spaces, workshop rooms, etc. for side events, and other activities
- **Exhibition: please contact potential exhibitors and provide them the link to PSO (professional congress organizer): Company C-IN, Prague, via:**

<https://www.iugg2023berlin.org/>

SELECTED ACTIVITIES OF DGK-DIVISIONS

Division “Education and Teaching”

(Goal: keep high quality level of university education and training in Germany and German speaking countries, contacts to universities of applied sciences)

- Meetings with representatives of different universities.
- in-depth exchange about current questions, problems and perspectives.
- questions about student numbers and student acquisition are regularly discussed.
- exchange on didactic issues was started in 2019
- **Digitization of all DGK publications is planned (since 1952 more than 1000 volumes)**
- **New: Task Force on Gender and Diversity (Chair Prof. A. Eicker, HCU Hamburg)**

NUMBER OF STUDENTS IN GERMANY

Abb. 1: Freshmen in Geodesy and Geoinformation at Universities in Germany

Abb. 2: Graduates from Universities in Germany

SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN TO ATTRACT STUDENTS

- Low number of students is in contrast to the great demand on the labor market.
- To attract students → social media campaign was launched by associations and universities in 2020.
- **Target group: high school pupils 14-17y**
- November 2019: summit at Leibniz Universität Hannover with leading representatives from DVW, AdV, BDVI, VDV, BKG, FGVK and **DGK**
- → agreed to implement the **social media campaign** as a national joint measure

Follower. 14. August – 3. November

DGK ANNUAL CONFERENCE ON 19.-21. SEPT. 2022
IN INNSBRUCK, AUSTRIA

Within the joint D-A-CH Meeting that is conducted every 5 years in one of the German speaking countries (DGK, ÖGK, SGK)

Main Focus:

- Alpine region, challenges for geodetic research
- Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS)

Next DGK Annual Conference in Munich: 22.-24.11.2023

CONTACT

Postal address:

DGK - AUSSCHUSS GEODÄSIE der
Bayerischen Akademie der
Wissenschaften
Alfons-Goppel-Str. 11
80539 München

www.dgk.badw.de
post@dgk.badw.de

DGK Office:

Acting Director Helmut Hornik
Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam Deutsches
GeoForschungsZentrum GFZ
Telegrafenberg
14473 Potsdam

Urgent requests:

Harald Schuh schuh@gfz-potsdam.de
Urs Hugentobler urs.hugentobler@tum.de

